

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF THE TRAINING COURSE IN THE SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOL AND SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the issues of pedagogical knowledge of teachers, which form the main components of professional competence, individual psychological characteristics, professional beliefs, work-related motivation and self-regulation as aspects of their professional competence. It also revealed the need to form indicators of professional orientation among students on the basis of differential differences in the manifestation of communicative, intellectual, emotional, regulatory characteristics, based on the presence of differences in the qualification category in the development of professional competence among public education employees, some suggestions and considerations for the development of professional competence are given.*

Keywords: *professional competence, communicative, intellectual, emotional, regulatory characteristics.*

In the world, in all aspects of human activity, ensuring professionalism and efficiency, training, retraining and upgrading of professional personnel are gaining urgent importance. It's no secret that the most important factor in solving problems and issues on the way to the development of society is creative, talented pedagogues with modern knowledge. According to the information of the UNESCO Institute of Statistics (UIS), "by 2030, there will be a need for more than 69 million quality pedagogues to provide primary and general secondary education around the world." In this regard, paying special attention to the researches aimed at learning the factors and tools that ensure the professional potential and effectiveness of pedagogues, which can form qualities such as desire for education and thirst for knowledge in students, remains one of the urgent problems today.

Determining the priorities for the systematic reform of general secondary education in the centers of world education and scientific research, raising the moral, moral and intellectual maturity of the growing young generation to a new level in terms of quality, educational - special attention is being paid to scientific research on the issues of introducing innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process. In this regard, there is a need to determine the psychological factors of the development of professional competence that directly affect the effectiveness of the pedagogical activity of the students of advanced training courses in the public education system, to determine the components that determine the basis of professional competence, and to pay attention to the measures aimed at finding content. .

In recent years, in our republic, "out of 504,000 pedagogues working in schools, 60,000 have secondary special education, and 190,000 have no qualification at all... the knowledge and skills of many pedagogues are insufficient" to determine the priorities of the systematic reform of general high school and extracurricular education, to raise the spiritual, moral and intellectual

development of the growing young generation to a new level in terms of quality, to promote the educational process. The necessary legal and normative frameworks for the introduction of innovative forms and methods of education, the development of the professional quality levels of public education workers, the improvement of the mechanisms of qualification improvement and retraining have been created.

Today, as a result of the innovative changes taking place in the education system, not only the level of knowledge, but also the knowledge and skills in a certain field of activity are of particular importance for the improvement of living conditions and the more effective development of a modern person.

Naturally, a person with a certain level of general or professional education will have the opportunity to engage in work, but if a person wants to take a decent place in a rapidly developing society, in order to increase work efficiency higher qualifications are required. Nowadays, the problem of competence development is gaining urgent importance.

In the 1970s, V. David, Mk. Research results were published by Clelland, which confirm that good mastery of educational programs and successful passing of test tests do not mean effective activity and its effectiveness, but that it is important to have competencies for this. Competence approach, as in all spheres of human activity, is of urgent importance in the education system.

In order to consider the process of development of the professional competence of public education workers in the process of qualification improvement, commenting on concepts such as "competence", "professional competence", "communicative competence", "professional competence of public education workers", "development", as well as , it is necessary to determine the requirements for the professional competence of public education workers in the system of professional development.

Competence is a word with many meanings, but the common point of all its definitions can be called the result of their connection with activities.

Competence means the meaning of motivation, character traits, social role of a person, knowledge and skills that correspond to the functional requirements of the work and the vision of the organization. "Competence" and "competence" are often used as closely related concepts.

E.F. Zeyer distinguishes the concepts of competence and competence separately. He argues that the concept of competence is broader than the concept of knowledge, skill or skill and includes them.

This concept has a slightly different semantic meaning, it includes not only cognitive, but also motivational, moral, social and educational aspects, as well as knowledge and skills, value system, skills, etc.

This concept embodies the components of education related to mental processes and skills. Core competence has an integrative nature, it includes skills and knowledge related to the same type or closely related culture and other areas of activity (management, information, legal, etc.) .

Competence means "the specialist's ability to successfully apply his knowledge, skills, as well as generalized methods of action in professional activity."

Core competencies ensure that a specialist is versatile and universal, so he may not be too specialized in one activity. Competence is manifested in certain situations (social and professional).

While researching the differences between the concepts of competence and competence, E.F. Zeyer states that "knowledge, skills, and experience define a person's competence, and it is the ability to mobilize this knowledge, skills, and experience in a specific social and professional situation."

V.A. Slastenin, I.F. Isayev, E.N. Different approaches are presented in Shiyonov's scientific works. According to this approach, competence means skills and abilities, and their level of development is interpreted as competence.

G.S. Professional competence is defined by Trofimova as "a talent built on professional, moral, individual-psychological qualities of a person and directed to ensure the efficiency indicators of professional activity, measures implemented due to the development of the level of activity of a person in social relations." Y.N. Emelyanova, L.A. According to Petrovsky's scientific views, the teacher's professional competence has a great place in easy and successful adaptation to various changing, unexpected situations, new demands imposed by society.

The analysis of the literature on the subject of the research shows that the attitude of the state, parents and the public to the processes taking place in educational organizations has changed. Now, in order to keep up with the times, public education workers need to harmonize the processes of development, teaching and upbringing of students. As the society develops rapidly, the need for a teacher with professional competence, who approaches the educational process responsibly, pays particular attention to the results of the activity, is increasing.

This, in turn, requires the staff of public education to strictly ensure that students master the knowledge, skills, and abilities specified in the state education standard, to perfect the ways of their comprehensive development as mature individuals. requires them to know.

M.A. In his scientific research, Choshanov uses the concept of competence as a set of skills and abilities, as well as the ability to perform an activity, the ability to have alternative methods of solving problems.

Based on the results of pedagogical observations, the specific characteristics of the professional activity of public education workers are as follows:

- correct understanding of students' role in the process of social development and students' sense of trust in the teacher;
- to ensure students' aspiration to progress in all aspects through proper use of various methods of support, encouragement, and respect for the student's personality;
- to correctly accept students' direct and various forms of appeals, to be able to understand the essence of the student's existing problems;
- ability to effectively communicate in "teacher-student" relationships and take responsibility for this;
- to determine methods of problem solving in order to normalize communicative relations, etc.

The main goal of research aimed at studying professional competence is its development and identification of factors affecting it. It is known that by development we understand the rise of things and events from one stage to the next, higher, more perfect stage. In philosophical dictionaries, the concept of development is explained as the characteristics of qualitative changes in objects, the emergence and formation of new forms of existence in nature.

In our research, it is considered important to analyze the structure of professional competence of public education workers and its development.

It can be concluded from the above that the content and structure of the professional competence of public education workers, as well as its improvement, allow us to more objectively evaluate and describe the ways of developing the professional competence of the teacher, which in turn, in the process of training includes creating a model of professional competence development.

Using the resources of the training system and taking into account the results of the research, the goal system of the educational organization was analyzed and the ways to achieve them were shown. Accordingly, a functional model of the training system (Fig. 1) was developed. In this model, the system, structure and their interrelationship related to the process of qualification improvement were revealed. During the experimental work, special attention was paid to the analysis of mutual cooperation of the Education Center of the regional public education department, methodical service of the district, city level, school methodical associations, creative groups of teachers.

In order for a modern teacher to effectively realize his professional potential, he must have a number of professional qualities, certain personal psychological qualities, and professional culture. All these are the most important factors of professional competence and professional success.

The disproportion and incompatibility of the professional position with the teacher's values and needs causes dissatisfaction with the activity and environment. The creation of an opportunity for self-expression in professional activity has a positive effect on the development of professional abilities of the teacher, their quantitative and indicators, and determines the effectiveness of pedagogical activity.

Professional self-awareness of public education workers is an indicator of professional competence and success - it indicates that they are ready to move to a new level of professional skills and use pedagogical innovations. The development of the teacher's professional competences and personal psychological characteristics allows them to learn the aspirations and knowledge, skills, personality of each student, to know the essence of their work, self-knowledge, self-esteem. and provides an opportunity to acquire psychoanalytical qualities that promote self-actualization in professional activities.

Through the information reflected in this program and their application, the individual-psychological characteristics of the representatives of the field, as well as professional and personal self-awareness, interest, ability and fulfillment of their goals as subjects of professional activity, innovative psychological serves in the positive implementation of the activity.

The task of the program: to develop theoretical knowledge by understanding the practical significance of psychological-pedagogical theoretical information and to arouse teachers' interest in the science of psychology, to develop the skills of using psychological-pedagogical knowledge to eliminate difficulties in practical activities, in which they have high formation of professional motivation, formation of a positive attitude towards the further development of professional activity and professional competence through the correct understanding of one's professional and personal qualities, formation of skills to search for new information and knowledge aimed at professional development and work with them.

The main focus of the program is on training sessions, and the purpose of the training is to develop important professional qualities, individual psychological characteristics, and professional competence of public education workers.

The burdens experienced by a teacher during his work have a negative effect on his individual characteristics and cause his vital energy to be spent inefficiently. Due to chronic overwork, the teacher cannot positively accept innovations in the field of education, in turn, he is not ready to improve his professional skills and success.

An important condition for maintaining and strengthening mental health in any profession related to stressful situations is the release of internal tension and proper organization of rest. One of the forms of effective support for the teacher is psychocorrection methods that help self-development and self-recovery. During the time spent on psychotechnical exercises, the teacher can get rid of fatigue and gain a state of inner calmness, stability, and self-confidence.

In most cases, teachers need social and psychological help, not medical help. It is necessary to develop the necessary qualities and skills in them and form the necessary forms of behavior to overcome difficult situations.

In the process of developing the professional competence of public education workers, motivation is the creation of effective mechanisms for the development of public education workers' professional competence.

Aspirations are important in the process of developing professional competence among public education workers, which indicates that the increase in professional efficiency depends on the educational process. It can be seen that professional motives are considered the main factor in improving the professional literacy of public education workers.

It is necessary to determine the motivations that encourage public education workers to familiarize themselves with the reforms implemented in our country, their results, scientific and technical achievements, and modern pedagogical technologies for managing the pedagogical process. Because these motives can have a positive effect on the scope of work of any employee working in an educational institution.

In educational institutions, the correct choice of the goal, which is determined in the harmony of general needs and the direction of meeting needs, is of special importance, that is, the psychological processes of public education employees, such as thinking and perception, increase their professional potential. acts as a developing force. The most important factor is the correct direction of internal aspirations.

In psychological sources, it is explained that motivation is an integral part of human life in a broad sense. Teachers' activities can be guided by various motives. The influence that creates voluntary behavior with the help of motives is considered effective, and the positive results of the activity depend on the correct selection of internal aspirations, which represents the effectiveness of the process of creating motivation.

In the process of developing the professional competence of public education workers, it determines how important national values, customs, and the results of the reforms implemented in our country are. This process is a complex system of public education workers, and the needs, beliefs, goals, desires, interests, demands, and tasks are the part that fills this system. In most scientific studies, when providing information on the relationship between learning motivation and learning efficiency, the level of thinking of a person is mentioned.

According to scientific studies, positive motivation can fill their place when the necessary skills are not enough. Otherwise, no amount of skill can replace motivation.

It is desirable to develop more interest in the field of education among pedagogues, based on certain needs, and to direct their activities through spiritual influence. In the process of motivation, first of all, the needs of public education workers should be taken into account.

In the process of developing the professional competence of public education workers, it is possible to motivate them to work, to form a positive attitude to the reforms and developments in the educational system, interest, and confidence in the future. The formation of professional motivation should be aimed at increasing the professional literacy of pedagogues by explaining their interests, skills and qualifications they are gaining in the process of training based on educational needs. To comprehensively encourage the development of the need to achieve success in teaching activities, to create conditions for the development of the professional competence of the pedagogue and to increase his prestige, to morally and materially encourage his achievements and help to remove the fear of possible failures in the situation of achieving them. it is appropriate to give. This opinion is especially characteristic of specialist teachers with long years of work experience, as Table 6 shows that they have a much lower motivation to strive for success than their senior colleagues.

Therefore, one of the factors that need to be paid special attention to in the effective organization of the pedagogical process for the development of professional competence among public education workers is the effectiveness of the motivation formation process.

According to the analysis of the results of the research, it was observed that the self-assessment scale of anxiety is relatively high in expert teachers, and it is almost close to the normal state in high-class pedagogues. According to the results of the study of the personality characteristics of the examinees, the listeners of the expert category have a slightly higher level of dependence on others, emotionality, self-confidence, realism, practicality, in some cases, harshness, and a rude attitude towards others. it was observed that the indicators of being, being easily influenced, the level of self-control, as well as the state of indifference and relaxation, low self-esteem, among high-class pedagogues, enterprising, creative search, professional tendency to development, responsibility, self-demand, confidence in one's own strength, courage, organization, self-respect, strong desire for innovation were clearly expressed. In the development of professional competence of pedagogues working in the system of public education, factors such as striving for success, intelligence, communication, subject orientation are important as important indicators that ensure the effectiveness of developmental measures.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуллаева Ш.Х. Социально-психологические основы профессиональной компетентности. «Наука и технологии». Монография. Ташкент.: «Наука и технологии», - 2017. - 180 с.
2. Баротов Ш.Р. Психологическая служба. // Учебник. – Ташкент: Навроз, 2018. – 334 с.
3. Каримова В. Основы профессиональной компетентности в управлении. Монография. / проф. В.М. Под редакцией Каримовой. – Т.: «Наука и техника», 2008. – 120 с.
4. Нишонова З.Т. Психологическая служба – Т.; 2006. – 156 с.
5. Фахретдинова М.А. Формирование профессиональной компетентности учителя / М.А. Фахретдинова // Профессиональное образование. - 2006. - № 3.-С. 32-38.
6. Хайтов О.Э. Моделирование психологической компетентности лидера. Автореф.псих.фан. док.дис. - Т.2020. – Б.34.